

Multi-actor collaboration dynamics and capacity building network inside and between AKIS to foster the upscaling of SFSCs across Europe

D.6.3 Elaboration of 15 Practice abstracts

Responsible partner: INNO

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History of changes

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Table 1: History of changes

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Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

Open Food Network: Empowering Farmers and Strengthening Short Food Supply Chains

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

The Open Food Network (www.openfoodnetwork.org) enables farmers to connect, sell, and collaborate efficiently through a user-friendly, low-cost online platform. Over 20,000 producers in 25 countries use OFN to manage their sales, create online shops, and even trade products from neighboring farms, forming local "Food Hubs" that strengthen community ties. Key outcomes include increased visibility, higher sales, and better planning for production and investments. The system supports both local and cross-border exchanges, helping farmers reach new markets and respond to consumer demand without heavy upfront costs. For practitioners, the main benefit is access to a scalable, open-source tool that simplifies marketing, logistics, and payments while fostering collaboration with other producers. By joining OFN, farmers can reduce operational costs, enhance productivity, and leverage collective bargaining power, turning digital connectivity into tangible economic and social value for their businesses and communities. Farmers can easily join by registering on their national OFN platform or through local support organisations that help set up community food hubs.

A practical example comes from France, where Les Halles du Touet and other regional cooperatives use OFN to coordinate weekly orders, aggregate produce from dozens of small farms, and offer consumers transparent, farmer-direct access to seasonal products. The platform has helped these cooperatives streamline logistics, stabilise income for producers, and strengthen rural-urban connections.

Short title in native language

Open Food Network: Potenziare le vendite agricole e rafforzare le filiere

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

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Open Food Network (OFN) è una piattaforma digitale open-source e a basso costo che consente agli agricoltori di vendere i propri prodotti, collaborare con altri produttori e creare "Food Hubs" locali. La piattaforma permette di aprire un negozio online in pochi clic, gestire vendite sia dei propri prodotti sia di quelli dei vicini e raggiungere clienti sia a livello locale sia internazionale, senza investimenti significativi in software o infrastrutture. L'adesione a OFN favorisce un incremento delle vendite, una pianificazione più accurata della produzione e una riduzione dei costi operativi legati a marketing e logistica. Inoltre, la collaborazione tra produttori consente di aumentare il potere contrattuale, creare mercati affidabili e rafforzare le comunità locali. Per le aziende agricole di piccole e medie dimensioni, OFN rappresenta uno strumento concreto per valorizzare la produzione locale, migliorare la sostenibilità economica e supportare lo sviluppo delle filiere corte.

Gli agricoltori possono aderire facilmente registrandosi sulla piattaforma OFN nazionale o tramite organizzazioni di supporto locali che aiutano a creare centri alimentari comunitari.

Un esempio pratico viene dalla Francia, dove Les Halles du Touet e altre cooperative regionali utilizzano OFN per coordinare gli ordini settimanali, aggregare i prodotti di decine di piccole aziende agricole e offrire ai consumatori un accesso trasparente e diretto ai prodotti stagionali. La piattaforma ha aiutato queste cooperative a snellire la logistica, stabilizzare il reddito dei produttori e rafforzare i collegamenti tra le zone rurali e quelle urbane.

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Agricultural Trade Regulation from France: The Role of G.I.E.

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In France, Economic Interest Groups (EIGs) are strategic levers for agricultural producers who want to cooperate without losing their autonomy. They facilitate market access, reduce transaction costs, and strengthen bargaining power, while enabling the sharing of innovations and joint investments (certifications, equipment, digital tools). For small and medium-sized farms, joining or creating an EIG offers major benefits: increased competitiveness, risk pooling, and reduced administrative burdens, while maintaining the legal independence of each member.

Example: the Chapeau de Paille EIG brings together 35 pick-your-own farms covering 550 hectares and welcomes 2 million visitors per year. This model has reduced logistics costs, improved commercial visibility, and created a central purchasing unit to optimize supplies.

From a legal standpoint, creating an EIG involves drafting a contract specifying the name, purpose, registered office, duration, information about the members, and the appointment of directors and their powers. No share capital is required, but at least two members must be engaged in an activity related to the purpose of the group.

In a competitive agricultural context, economic interest groups are powerful and low-risk tools for strengthening resilience and supporting the agroecological transition, focusing on cooperation rather than concentration.

Short title in native language

Réglementation du commerce agricole en France : le rôle des G.I.E.

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

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En France, les Groupements d'Intérêt Économique (G.I.E.) sont des leviers stratégiques pour les producteurs agricoles souhaitant coopérer sans perdre leur autonomie. Ils facilitent l'accès aux marchés, réduisent les coûts de transaction et renforcent le pouvoir de négociation, tout en permettant le partage d'innovations et d'investissements communs (certifications, équipements, outils numériques).

Pour les petites et moyennes exploitations, rejoindre ou créer un G.I.E. offre des bénéfices majeurs : compétitivité accrue, mutualisation des risques et allègement des charges administratives, tout en conservant l'indépendance juridique de chaque membre.

Exemple : le G.I.E. Chapeau de Paille regroupe 35 cueillettes sur 550 ha, accueille 2 millions de visiteurs par an. Ce modèle a permis de réduire les coûts logistiques, d'améliorer la visibilité commerciale et de créer une centrale d'achat pour optimiser les approvisionnements.

Sur le plan juridique, la création d'un G.I.E. implique la rédaction d'un contrat précisant : dénomination, objet, siège social, durée, informations sur les membres, puis la désignation des dirigeants et leurs pouvoirs. Aucun capital social n'est requis, mais au moins deux membres doivent exercer une activité liée à l'objet du groupement.

Dans un contexte agricole concurrentiel, les G.I.E. sont des outils puissants et peu risqués pour renforcer la résilience et accompagner la transition agroécologique, en misant sur la coopération plutôt que la concentration.

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Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

Registration of the trademark of the Szekler Product and development of the control methodology, organisation of monthly fairs in Harghita County

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

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Following community requests, the Harghita County Council identified barriers for small producers, including fear of inspections, limited market access, and low consumer awareness. To address this, it launched monthly local product fairs and introduced the Székely Termék Trademark to ensure quality and authenticity. Inspectors attended fairs to advise producers, reducing mistrust and improving compliance. Supported by €40,000 annually and later European projects, the initiative covered fairs, staffing, and producer training. Around 200 farmers, public institutions, Sapientia University, and farmers' organisations participated. Fair organisation and trademark management moved to the Harghita County Development Agency, with an NGO overseeing control. Producers are monitored for legal and food safety compliance, and consumer habits are tracked. Launched in 2010, Székely Termék links quality assurance with direct sales. Criteria require local raw materials and processing in Szeklerland, assessed via a points system on traceability, compliance, and producer activity. A premium category for higher-quality and organic products is in development. Farmers joined due to immediate sales, strong promotion, low entry barriers, and training. The initiative boosted consumer trust, institutional cooperation, producer professionalism, and sustainable support, showing the impact of county-level leadership in Romania.

Short title in native language

Marca Comercială Produs Secuiesc

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

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Ca răspuns la solicitările comunității, Consiliul Județean Harghita a identificat barierele pentru micii producători: teama de controale, acces limitat la piață și conștientizare scăzută a consumatorilor. Pentru a le depăși, au fost lansate târguri lunare de produse locale și marca Székely Termék pentru a garanta calitatea și autenticitatea. Autoritățile de control au participat la târguri pentru a oferi consultanță directă, reducând neîncrederea și îmbunătățind conformitatea. Inițiativa a fost susținută cu 40.000 € anual și, ulterior, prin proiecte europene, acoperind organizarea târgurilor, personalul și instruirea producătorilor. Aproximativ 200 de fermieri, instituții publice, Universitatea Sapientia și organizații ale fermierilor au participat. Organizarea târgurilor și gestionarea mărcii au fost preluate de Agenția de Dezvoltare Județeană Harghita, iar controlul mărcii de un ONG. Producătorii sunt monitorizați pentru conformitatea legală și siguranța alimentară, iar obiceiurile consumatorilor sunt evaluate constant. Lansată în 2010, marca Székely Termék leagă asigurarea calității de vânzarea directă. Criteriile cer materii prime locale și procesare în Ținutul Secuiesc, evaluate printr-un sistem de puncte privind trasabilitatea, conformitatea și activitatea producătorilor. Este în dezvoltare o categorie premium pentru produse organice și de calitate superioară. Inițiativa a crescut încrederea consumatorilor, cooperarea între fermieri și instituții, profesionalizarea producătorilor și crearea unor structuri de sprijin durabile, evidențiind importanța conducerii

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Short title in English

AMPI CSA Network: Building Farmer Knowledge, Capacity, and Local Food Sovereignty

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

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The AMPI CSA Network supports farmers and consumers in building fair, transparent, and community-led local food systems in Czechia. By coordinating Community Supported Agriculture (CSA) groups, AMPI helps farmers plan production, organise logistics, and secure stable, low-risk markets. A key feature is its strong focus on knowledge and capacity building. Through its accredited Farm School, AMPI provides hands-on training, mentoring, and peer-to-peer learning that helps new entrants gain practical skills and confidence.

Main outcomes include better access to knowledge, reduced entry barriers for new farmers, increased consumer awareness of local food, and a growing national CSA movement serving thousands of households. For practitioners, the AMPI model offers a proven, replicable approach that reduces marketing costs, supports better production planning, and strengthens long-term relationships with committed consumers. By using AMPI's advisory services and training opportunities, farmers can improve resilience, increase economic stability, and become part of a supportive and knowledgeable CSA community.

More information: www.asociaceampi.cz; www.kpzinfo.cz; www.farmarskaskola.cz

Short title in native language

Síť KPZ AMPI: Budování znalostí, kapacit a místní potravinové

Short summary for practitioners in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

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Síť KPZ AMPI podporuje ekologické farmáře a spotřebitele při budování férových, transparentních a komunitně řízených místních potravinových systémů v České republice. Koordinací skupin KPZ AMPI pomáhá farmářům lépe plánovat produkci, organizovat logistiku a získat stabilní odbytiště s nižším rizikem. Klíčovou součástí práce AMPI je rozvoj znalostí a kapacit. Prostřednictvím akreditované Farmářské školy poskytuje AMPI praktické vzdělávání, mentoring a vzájemné učení mezi farmáři, což novým entrantům výrazně usnadňuje vstup do ekologického zemědělství.

Hlavní výsledky zahrnují lepší přístup ke znalostem, snazší start pro nové farmáře, posílení povědomí o místních potravinách a růst sítě KPZ napříč republikou. Pro praxi je model AMPI osvědčeným a přenositelným nástrojem, který snižuje náklady na marketing, podporuje efektivnější plánování produkce a posiluje dlouhodobé vztahy mezi farmáři a spotřebiteli. Využitím poradenských a vzdělávacích aktivit AMPI mohou farmáři zvýšit svou odolnost, ekonomickou stabilitu a stát se součástí podpůrné a znalostně silné komunity KPZ.

Více informací: www.asociaceampi.cz

- www.kpzinfo.cz
- www.farmarskaskola.cz

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Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

Short Food Supply Chains in Italy: Legal Definitions and Opportunities for Farmers

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

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Italy has recently introduced clear rules defining “zero-kilometer” and short food supply chain (SFSC) products, making it easier for farmers to market local, fresh, and seasonal products directly to consumers. Under the law (Law No. 61 of May 17, 2022), short supply chain products can have at most one intermediary, while zero-kilometer products must originate within 70 km of the sale point. This clarity enables farmers to confidently promote the origin and quality of their products, increase transparency, and strengthen local connections. Practically, farmers can leverage these regulations to expand their market reach, build collaborative “Food Hubs,” and participate in public procurement projects, such as supplying schools or local institutions. By understanding and using these definitions, producers can reduce marketing uncertainty, improve competitiveness, and foster stronger relationships with consumers and other local operators. Clear legal definitions also facilitate access to support programs, funding, and networking opportunities, empowering farmers to scale their businesses while enhancing local food systems.

Short title in native language

Filiera corta e prodotti a chilometro zero in Italia: le normative e le

Short summary for practitioners in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

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In Italia sono state recentemente introdotte norme più chiare per la definizione dei prodotti a chilometro zero e della filiera corta, agevolando gli agricoltori nella commercializzazione diretta di prodotti freschi, locali e stagionali. Secondo la legislazione (Legge 17 maggio 2022, n. 61), i prodotti della filiera corta possono prevedere al massimo un intermediario, mentre i prodotti a chilometro zero devono provenire da una distanza non superiore ai 70 km dal luogo di vendita. Queste definizioni consentono agli agricoltori di promuovere con certezza l'origine e la qualità dei propri prodotti, aumentare la trasparenza e rafforzare il legame con il territorio. Sul piano pratico, gli agricoltori possono sfruttare tali norme per ampliare il mercato di riferimento, creare “Food Hub” collaborativi e partecipare a progetti di approvvigionamento pubblico, come la fornitura di mense scolastiche e istituzioni locali. La comprensione e l'applicazione di queste definizioni aiutano i produttori a ridurre l'incertezza commerciale, migliorare la competitività e sviluppare relazioni solide con consumatori e altri operatori locali. Inoltre, le regole facilitano l'accesso a programmi di sostegno, finanziamenti e opportunità di networking, permettendo alle aziende agricole di crescere valorizzando i sistemi alimentari locali.

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Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

Legal Definition of Agricultural Activity in Italy: Enabling Small-Scale and Local Food Production

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) **outcomes** (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

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Italy has established clear legal frameworks to define agricultural activity, supporting small-scale, local, and short supply chain production. Two key laws—Law 30/2022 and Law 61/2022—clarify what constitutes agricultural and fishery production, including primary products and limited local processing. These laws set principles for food safety, localization, limited production volumes, and product specificity, allowing farmers to produce and sell locally, including in educational or experimental farm settings. For practitioners, this legal clarity helps confidently organize production, marketing, and direct sales while ensuring compliance with hygiene and labeling rules. Farmers can take advantage of simplified administrative procedures, access targeted training, and use promotional tools such as official logos to communicate product origin and authenticity. The framework also fosters cooperation with local authorities, educational institutions, and other producers, facilitating public procurement and local market participation. By understanding these laws, practitioners can reduce legal uncertainty, improve consumer trust, expand their market reach, and strengthen the economic and social impact of their farm activities.

Short title in native language

Definizione legale dell'attività agricola in Italia: sostegno alla produzione

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

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In Italia sono state introdotte normative chiare per definire l'attività agricola e ittica, sostenendo la produzione su piccola scala, locale e all'interno di filiere corte. Le leggi principali—L. 30/2022 e L. 61/2022—stabiliscono i criteri per identificare i prodotti primari e trasformati derivanti dalla produzione aziendale, fissando principi fondamentali quali salubrità, localizzazione, limitatezza della produzione e specificità del prodotto. Queste norme consentono agli agricoltori di organizzare in sicurezza la produzione, la commercializzazione e la vendita diretta, inclusi contesti didattici o sperimentali, rispettando le regole igienico-sanitarie e di etichettatura. I professionisti possono beneficiare di procedure amministrative semplificate, percorsi formativi mirati e strumenti di valorizzazione come loghi ufficiali per comunicare origine e autenticità dei prodotti. Inoltre, le leggi favoriscono la collaborazione con enti locali, istituti scolastici e altri produttori, agevolando la partecipazione a mercati locali e appalti pubblici. La piena comprensione di queste disposizioni permette agli operatori di ridurre l'incertezza legale, rafforzare la fiducia dei consumatori, ampliare la propria rete di mercato e aumentare l'impatto economico e sociale delle attività agricole.

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Short title in English

Optimizing logistics to lower carbon emissions and enhance operational efficiency - the case of food hubs

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) **outcomes** (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

Food hubs serve as platforms that aggregate products from small-scale food producers and facilitate their delivery to final consumers, which can enhance their profit margins and foster local economic development. However, the logistics involved in operating food hubs can be particularly costly and often involves small volume journeys. This research aimed to address the 'producer-to-hub-to-customer' transport problem and optimise efficiency in operational logistics while considering economic (costs) and environmental aspects (carbon emissions). Main results: We developed a mathematical model and performed computational experiments using data from a regional food hub featuring products from over 150 producers across North East England. The research empirically shows that enhancing (horizontal) cooperation among producers when delivering goods to the hub can improve vehicle utilisation and the efficiency of their supply chain network and lead to a reduction in both logistics costs and carbon emissions by 12-16%. The study also indicates that switching from conventional to electric vehicles can reduce transport costs by nearly one-third and diminish carbon emissions by as much as 70%. Importantly, visualising data helps better understand performance metrics and optimise logistics. Practical recommendations: The research demonstrates the possibilities of improving the environmental and operational efficiency in food hubs' logistics. Specifically, it provides practical insights for food hub operators and their suppliers (inc. small-scale food producers), as well as third party logistics providers to short food supply chain operators. The analysis is also of relevance to local and regional economic development bodies

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Short title in native language

Short summary for practitioners in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

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Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

ROMO: Innovative network connecting local producers with consumers

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

The founders of ROMO faced a major market access barrier: although they produced high-quality, ethically raised poultry on their micro-farm, strict retail requirements prevented sales through traditional channels. This common challenge for micro-scale producers led to the creation of ROMO, a model that connects local producers directly with consumers and simplifies sales for small agricultural and artisanal food businesses.

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ROMO aims to remove retail barriers, offer consumers access to high-quality, local, ethically produced food, and build a community-based marketplace that supports local economies and sustainable food systems. Inspired by Finland's REKO network, the initiative gained momentum during the COVID-19 pandemic, which exposed weaknesses in conventional food supply chains and increased demand for local alternatives. A typical weekly order includes products from 3–5 producers, such as vegetables, dairy, bread, eggs, meat, and artisanal goods, reflecting the platform's diversity. Consumers join local ROMO Facebook groups, place weekly pre-orders by commenting on producers' posts, and collect orders at fixed pickup points. Interactions are direct, public, and transparent. Producers apply through an online pre-selection process, must meet quality and legal standards, and receive positive customer feedback. Approved producers post weekly offers, prepare only pre-ordered quantities, and deliver them at

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Short title in native language

ROMO: de la Producător direct la Consumator – Platformă inovatoare

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

ROMO este o platformă de vânzare directă de tip comunitar, care conectează peste 160 de producători locali cu consumatorii printr-un sistem bazat pe precomenzi săptămânale și puncte fixe de ridicare (activă în 2 mari orașe: București și Brașov), organizate prin grupuri locale de Facebook. Din 2020 până în prezent, ROMO a facilitat peste 13.939.000 lei în vânzări (~€2.8 million), a onorat peste 200.000 de comenzi în cadrul a 799 de întâlniri și a crescut o comunitate de peste 50.000 de membri. Inspirat de modelul finlandez REKO și adaptat contextului românesc, ROMO contribuie la reducerea risipei alimentare, sprijină agricultura etică și regenerativă și profesionalizează lanțurile scurte de aprovizionare.

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Beneficii practice principale:

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- Pentru producători: venituri stabile și previzibile, risc redus, fără risipă, vizibilitate crescută și acces direct la clienți, fără infrastructură digitală complexă sau costuri mari.

- Pentru consumatori: acces săptămânal la hrană locală, proaspătă, trasabilă, cu o relație directă și transparentă cu producătorii.

- Pentru practicieni: modelul ROMO este ușor de replicat, bazat pe precomenzi, logistică transparentă și implicare comunitară pe rețele sociale. Se recomandă extinderea în alte regiuni, parteneriate cu restaurante și institutii precum și investitii în educație și logistică

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Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

Practice for Microcredentials

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

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recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

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A microcredential is a short, focused learning program that certifies mastery of a specific skill or competency. In short supply chains, where high variability exists, there is a strong need for flexible learning, as each actor possesses different knowledge. Lifelong learning is increasingly difficult to actively pursue alongside work, as very little time is available for continuous skill development. Due to the lack of harmonized definitions and frameworks for micro-credentials within SFSC contexts and to facilitate advisory recognition and collaboration in the SFSCs it was necessary to create modular and flexible pathways that support lifelong learning and knowledge consistency via certificated learning materials. By creating micro-credentials to each, freely accessible module, members of the SFSC systems can learn according to their knowledge, since smaller learning units allow users to acquire relevant expertise in smaller segments and relatively quickly, with each certificate guaranteeing validated competence. Furthermore, micro-credentials enable future full accreditation at the national level, as the process is not significantly different from that of complete curricula that would provide end-users with a unified framework that is easily interpretable across Europe, like the EQF system. This would improve applicability, foster greater acceptance, and facilitate smoother integration into the AKIS system as well as the accreditation of SFSC advisors in the long run. Furthermore, microcredentials are easily enlargeable and updateable offering a good base for further learning materials as well. The micro-credentials will be available for the developed 8 modules based on the targeted needs from SFSC advisors containing food production and technology innovation, digitalization

Short title in native language

Mikrotanúsítványok a projektben

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

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A mikrotanúsítványok egy rövid, célzott tanulási forma, amely egy adott készség vagy kompetencia elsajátítását igazolja. A rövid ellátási láncokban, ahol nagy a változékonyság, különösen fontos a rugalmas tanulás, mert az egyes szereplők nagyon eltérő tudással rendelkeznek, de az élethosszig tartó tanulás azonban egyre nehezebben fér össze a munkával, mivel kevés idő jut a folyamatos készségfejlesztésre. Mivel a rövid élelmiszer-ellátási láncok területén még nincs egységes keretrendszer a mikrotanúsítványokra vonatkozóan, szükség volt olyan moduláris és rugalmas tanulási utak kialakítására, amelyek támogatják az egység létrehozását és a fejlődést tanúsított tananyagok segítségével. Az egyes, szabadon hozzáférhető modulokhoz készített mikrotanúsítványok lehetővé teszik, hogy minden résztvevő a saját előzetes tudásának megfelelő szinten tanuljon. A kisebb tananyagegységek gyorsan elvégezhetőek, és minden modul elvégzése igazolt, hiteles kompetenciát jelent ezek segítségével. A mikrotanúsítványok hosszú távon akár teljes körű, nemzeti szintű akkreditáció alapjául is szolgálhatnak, mivel a létrehozásuk folyamata nem különbözik jelentősen egy teljes tanterv kidolgozásától és akkreditálásától. Így olyan egységes, Európa-szerte könnyen értelmezhető keretrendszer hozható létre, mint például az EQF. Ez növeli a gyakorlati alkalmazhatóságot, elősegíti a szélesebb elfogadottságot, támogatja az AKIS rendszerbe való beilleszkedést, és hosszú távon megkönnyítheti az SFSC tanácsadók személyes akkreditációját is. Ezek a tanúsítványok könnyen bővíthetőek és frissíthetőek, így jó alapot nyújtanak további tananyagfejlesztéshez is. A mikrotanúsítványok a kidolgozott 8 modulhoz lesznek elérhetőek, amelyek az rövid ellátási láncok tanácsadói igények alapján készültek. A modulok témái többek között az élelmiszer-termelés és -technológia, innováció, digitalizáció, marketing, címkézés, valamint fontos soft skilllek. Ezek gyors, személyre szabott, megbízható és időben rugalmas tanulást tesznek lehetővé, nyelvi akadályok nélkül, mivel könnyen

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

Herenboeren (Gentlemen's Farms)

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

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Herenboeren is a rapidly growing citizen movement demonstrating that the production of our daily food can be different, better, and above all, more sustainable. A Herenboerderij (Gentlemen's Farm) is owned by a cooperative of 200+ households who distribute the harvest among themselves. As a cooperative member of a nature-driven Herenboerderij, you take control of your own food production. The first Herenboerderij, Herenboeren Wilhelminapark, started in 2016 in Boxtel. As of September 2025, there are 23 Herenboeren farms, with over 9000 members in total.

A Herenboerderij is a legally registered cooperative UA (Except from Liable) of approximately 200-270 members (household). They are setting up a Herenboerderij within the 3 pillars and 7 principles of the Herenboeren concept and thus join the national Herenboeren movement. One of the principles of the Herenboerderijen is that the Herenboerderijen can run without 'external capital' and subsidies. The members use their own money to make the establishment of the farm possible. In principle, you commit to the cooperative for three years. If you unsubscribe earlier, you can get your deposit back under certain conditions. Inquire about this at your local Herenboerderij.

Short title in native language

Herenboeren

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Herenboeren is een snelgroeiende burgerbeweging die laat zien dat de productie van ons dagelijks voedsel anders, beter en vooral duurzamer kan. Een Herenboerderij is eigendom van een coöperatie van meer dan 200 huishoudens die de oogst onderling verdelen. Als coöperatielid van een natuurgerichte Herenboerderij neem je de controle over je eigen voedselproductie. De eerste Herenboerderij, Herenboeren Wilhelminapark, is in 2016 in Boxtel van start gegaan. In september 2025 zijn er 23 Herenboerenboerderijen, met in totaal meer dan 9000 leden.

Een Herenboerderij is een wettelijk geregistreerde coöperatie UA (Uitzonderlijk Aansprakelijk) met ongeveer 200-270 leden (huishoudens). Zij richten een Herenboerderij op binnen de 3 pijlers en 7 principes van het Herenboerenconcept en sluiten zich daarmee aan bij de landelijke Herenboerenbeweging. Een van de principes van de Herenboerderijen is dat de Herenboerderijen zonder 'extern kapitaal' en subsidies kunnen draaien. De leden gebruiken hun eigen geld om de oprichting van de boerderij mogelijk te maken. In principe verbindt u zich voor drie jaar aan de coöperatie. Als u zich eerder uitschrijft, kunt u onder bepaalde voorwaarden uw aanbetaling terugkrijgen. Informeer hiernaar bij uw lokale Herenboerderij (in aanbouw).

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Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

Baumschule Kastanienkultur: a small-scale woody crop nursery growing the foundation of regenerative, regional food systems

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

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The resilience and productivity of short food supply chains (SFSCs) can be strengthened by agroforestry systems (AFS). AFS do this by integrating trees and shrubs into farming systems to diversify food and income, buffer climate impacts, and enhance soil health and water cycling. Especially important are nut crops, which provide a perennial source of carbohydrates, fats, and proteins that are easy to store and process—an eco-friendly alternative to annual staple crops. A key barrier for AFS adoption in Europe is access to suitable woody plant material. Tree nurseries are often distant, lack appropriate species, and rely on intransparent supply chains and plant trading—affecting trust, quality, and crop success. Regional nurseries producing appropriate, seed-grown woody crop seedlings are vital for AFS and SFSCs yet are scarce. Baumschule Kastanienkultur (BK) in Germany is a unique small-scale tree and shrub nursery addressing a major gap in both AFS and SFSCs by growing specialized plants from seed, grafting if needed, and selling seedlings directly to regional customers establishing AFS. BK focuses on niche crops that meet urgent needs of regenerative, regional food systems in Germany—sweet chestnut, hazelnut and nitrogen-fixing trees. It centers on blight-resistant chestnut—a neglected high-potential crop. BK is one of Germany's only chestnut-focused nurseries. Trees are grown in air-pruning pots for strong, healthy roots, unlike many nurseries where root circling or lab cloning weakens tree vitality. BK also provides expert advice to help select trees for each location and need. They aim to build a genetic foundation for regenerative local food systems through in-house testing of hybrids for traits such as disease resistance, taste, local adaptability, and peel quality, using dedicated

Short title in native language

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Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

How Europe Supports Short Food Supply Chains: A Cross-Country Look at Advice, Training and Practical Opportunities for Farmers

Short summary for practitioners in english on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

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Farmers across Europe face fragmented support for Short Food Supply Chains (SFSC). While SFSCs improve income and resilience, regulatory complexity and lack of time often hinder their growth. This summary identifies how structured advice and informal networks help producers overcome these barriers.

Main Outcomes: Support systems vary significantly by country. In Austria, France, Estonia, and the Czech Republic, strong public advisory services provide structured guidance on food safety compliance and business planning. This reduces entrepreneurial risk and administrative burden. Conversely, in Croatia, Ireland, and Malta, knowledge relies on informal peer-to-peer networks and NGOs. While these drive local innovation, the lack of official advice can slow down scaling and regulatory alignment.

Support is most effective when it combines regulatory guidance with hands-on marketing advice, helping farmers translate complex labeling and safety rules into simple, step-by-step actions.

What farmers can do:

- Join local networks and cooperatives: Sharing best practices through peer-to-peer exchange is a powerful resource for learning and innovation.
- Access targeted training: Use webinars and demo events to master logistics, digital marketing, and pricing strategies.
- Seek integrated advice: Look for services that bridge the gap between technical production and business management to capture higher value and build customer loyalty.

Short title in native language

Hoe Europa korte voedselketens ondersteunt: een vergelijkend

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

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Boeren in Europa ervaren ongelijkmatige steun voor korte voedselketens (SFSC). Hoewel deze ketens het inkomen en de veerkracht vergroten, vormen complexe regelgeving en tijdgebrek vaak grote barrières. Dit overzicht laat zien hoe gestructureerd advies en informele netwerken producenten helpen deze obstakels te overwinnen.

Belangrijkste resultaten Ondersteuningssystemen verschillen sterk per land. In Oostenrijk, Frankrijk, Estland en Tsjechië bieden sterke publieke adviesdiensten gestructureerde begeleiding bij de naleving van voedselveiligheid en bedrijfsplanning. Dit vermindert ondernemersrisico's en administratieve lasten. In landen als Kroatië, Ierland en Malta vertrouwt kennis daarentegen op informele peer-to-peer netwerken en NGO's. Hoewel dit lokale innovatie stimuleert, kan het gebrek aan officieel advies opschaling en afstemming op regelgeving vertragen.

Ondersteuning is het meest effectief wanneer regelgevende begeleiding wordt gecombineerd met praktisch marketingadvies, waardoor complexe regels voor etikettering en veiligheid worden vertaald naar eenvoudige, stapsgewijze acties.

Wat boeren kunnen doen:

Sluit u aan bij lokale netwerken en coöperaties: Het delen van 'best practices' via onderlinge uitwisseling (peer-to-peer) is een krachtig hulpmiddel voor leren en innovatie.

Maak gebruik van gerichte training: Gebruik webinars en demonstratie-evenementen om logistiek, digitale marketing en prijsstrategieën te beheersen.

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Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

Horta-Cuina SAT: Enhancing Farmer Economic Stability Through School Catering Partnerships

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

Horta-Cuina, a Valencian Agricultural Transformation Society (SAT), demonstrates how small and medium-scale agroecological producers can enhance economic stability by accessing school catering markets. Main outcomes include: improved financial security for participating farms, sector professionalization through specialized supply-demand planning training, and developed capacity to meet collective catering volumes and standards.

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recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

Key practical recommendations: Farmers can diversify sales channels beyond traditional markets by securing regular contracts that guarantee stable demand and fair prices. Producer cooperation through SAT structures enables shared logistics costs and meeting educational centers' volume requirements.

Concrete economic benefits: Elimination of intermediaries, medium-term contracts facilitating financial planning, and reduced commercial costs through local sales. Agroecological producers can replicate this model by forming similar agricultural cooperatives, contacting school canteens in their territory, and specializing in seasonal local products demanded by collective catering.

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Short title in native language

Horta-Cuina SAT: Mejorando la estabilidad económica de agricultores a

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

Horta-Cuina, una Sociedad Agraria de Transformación (SAT) valenciana, demuestra cómo pequeños y medianos productores agroecológicos pueden mejorar su estabilidad económica accediendo al mercado de comedores escolares. Principales resultados incluyen: mayor seguridad financiera para explotaciones participantes, profesionalización del sector mediante formación especializada en planificación oferta-demanda, y desarrollo de capacidades para cumplir volúmenes y estándares de restauración colectiva.

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Recomendaciones prácticas clave: Los agricultores pueden diversificar canales de venta más allá de mercados tradicionales, asegurando contratos regulares que garantizan demanda estable y precios justos. La cooperación entre productores a través de estructuras SAT permite compartir costes logísticos y cumplir volúmenes requeridos por centros educativos.

Beneficios económicos concretos: Eliminación de intermediarios, contratos a medio plazo que facilitan planificación financiera, y reducción de costes comerciales mediante venta local. Los productores agroecológicos pueden replicar este modelo formando cooperativas agrarias similares, contactando comedores escolares de su territorio, y especializándose en productos locales de temporada demandados por la restauración colectiva.

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Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

Land van Ons (Land of Ours) - a thriving citizen collective for ecosystem and agricultural restoration

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

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recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Land van Ons ("Land of Us" - <https://landvanons.nl/>) was launched in the Netherlands in 2019 to democratize land ownership by enabling citizens to collectively invest in and manage farmland, restore biodiversity and landscape, and support sustainable, profitable farming while countering land concentration. "As a cooperative, Land of Us buys agricultural land on behalf of its participants. On this land, we restore biodiversity and landscape. Tenant farmers can farm profitably. Participating is easy."

Land van Ons buys land with participant contributions; every member has the same influence whether they invest €10,000 or €20. Individuals and groups buy shares and become co-owners who help decide on land management, sustainability practices and strategy, while tenant farmers implement agreed nature-inclusive methods.

Since 2019, Land van Ons has acquired over 400 ha and has about 30,000 paying members; by mid-2025 it managed roughly 360 ha over 26 plots. The latest Annual Report (2023) shows a solid financial profile: a net €5.0 million in member contribution; total equity increased in 2023 to €22.4 million (+30%); €7.1 million was invested in new plots, compared to €6.2 million in 2022.

The cooperative has no director. The board monitors implementation by national and local volunteer teams and is accountable to the General Assembly. Most work is unpaid, enabled by many participants contributing time and expertise, and external professionals are hired when needed.

Short title in native language

Land van Ons

Short summary for practitioners in native language (*can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English*) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

– Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)

– The **main practical**

recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

Land van Ons werd in 2019 in Nederland opgericht om grondbezit te democratiseren door burgers in staat te stellen gezamenlijk te investeren in en beheer te voeren over landbouwgrond, de biodiversiteit en het landschap te herstellen en duurzame, winstgevende landbouw te ondersteunen, terwijl grondconcentratie wordt tegengegaan. "Als coöperatie koopt Land van Ons landbouwgrond namens haar deelnemers. Op deze grond herstellen we de biodiversiteit en het landschap. Pachtboeren kunnen winstgevend landbouw bedrijven. Deelnemen is eenvoudig." Land van Ons koopt land met bijdragen van deelnemers; elk lid heeft dezelfde invloed, of hij nu € 10.000 of € 20 investeert. Individuen en groepen kopen aandelen en worden mede-eigenaren die mee beslissen over landbeheer, duurzaamheidspraktijken en strategie, terwijl pachtboeren overeengekomen natuurvriendelijke methoden toepassen.

Sinds 2019 heeft Land van Ons meer dan 4 miljoen m² (300 ha) verworven en heeft het ongeveer 30.000 betalende leden; medio 2025 beheerde het ongeveer 360 ha verdeeld over 26 percelen. Het laatste jaarverslag (2023) laat een solide financieel profiel zien: een nettobedrag van € 5,0 miljoen aan bijdragen van leden. Het totale eigen vermogen steeg in 2023 tot € 22,4 miljoen (+30%). Er werd € 7,1 miljoen geïnvesteerd in nieuwe percelen, tegenover € 6,2 miljoen in 2022. De coöperatie heeft geen directeur; het bestuur houdt toezicht op de uitvoering door nationale en lokale vrijwilligersteams en legt verantwoording af aan de algemene vergadering. Het meeste werk wordt onbetaald gedaan, dankzij de tijd en expertise die veel deelnemers inbrengen; indien nodig worden externe professionals ingehuurd.

Several practice abstracts may be needed for one project, depending on the size of the project and the number of outcomes/recommendations which are ready for practice.

Practice "abstract" 1:

Short title in English

The Roll-out of a Robust, Regional and Regenerative Food System in the Amsterdam Metropolitan Area

Short summary for practitioners in English on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). *Do not complete if the summary below is completed in English*

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

The "Roll-out of a Robust, Regional and Regenerative Food System in the Amsterdam Metropolitan Area (AMA)", initiated by Amped in 2019, uses collaboration and data to build a regionalised food economy. The AMA hosts many food-transition initiatives, but they have historically operated in isolation. Complexity arises from misaligned EU, national, provincial and municipal policies, which intersect at the regional level. The GAIN Transition Model provides a framework to build trust, collaborate and develop markets among actors who share a vision of a connected regional food system. Within 3 years, this consortium grew to 150 companies, organisations and (semi-)government bodies, 5 farmer collectives (500+ farmers) in and around the AMA, the business district, 2 large caterers and 3 universities. For SFSC farmers, it created leverage and revenue in a tough market, while policymakers gained insights and options for policies. The process inspired the Municipality of Amsterdam to invite Amped to co-write the city's Food Strategy 2023–2026.

In 2023, the roll-out was activated in Utrecht. Drawing on AMA lessons, collaboration accelerated and practical results were achieved within a year, with 80+ participating parties: local food initiatives, farmers, restoration groups, business and social enterprises and Utrecht University, working on 5 SFSC and regeneration projects, funding trajectories for scaling, young-entrepreneur programmes and research projects.

Short title in native language

De Uitrol van een Robuust, Regionaal en Regeneratief Voedselsysteem

Short summary for practitioners in native language (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise in English) (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces).

This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main **results/outcomes** of the activity (expected or final)
- The **main practical recommendation(s)**: what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for farmers/end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out entrepreneurial elements which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

De 'Uitrol van een robuust, regionaal en regeneratief voedselsysteem in de Metropoolregio Amsterdam (MRA)', door Amped in 2019 gestart, maakt gebruik van samenwerking en data om een geregionaliseerde voedsel economie op te bouwen. De MRA kent veel initiatieven op het gebied van voedseltransitie, maar deze hebben in het verleden altijd geïsoleerd van elkaar gewerkt.

De complexiteit ontstaat door onderling niet op elkaar afgestemd beleid van de EU, de nationale overheid, de provincies en de gemeenten, dat op regionaal niveau elkaar kruist. Het GAIN Transitie model biedt een kader om vertrouwen op te bouwen, samen te werken en markten te ontwikkelen tussen actoren die een visie delen op een verbonden regionaal voedselsysteem. Binnen drie jaar groeide dit consortium uit tot 150 bedrijven, organisaties en (semi-)overheidsinstanties, vijf boerencollectieven (meer dan 500 boeren) in en rond de AMA, het zakendistrict, twee grote cateraars en drie universiteiten.

Voor SFSC-boeren creëerde dit hefboomwerking en inkomsten in een moeilijke markt, terwijl beleidsmakers inzichten en opties voor beleid verkregen. Het proces inspireerde de gemeente Amsterdam om Amped uit te nodigen om mee te schrijven aan de Voedselstrategie 2023-2026 van de stad.

In 2023 werd de uitrol geactiveerd in Utrecht. Voortbouwend op de lessen van MRA werd de samenwerking versneld en werden binnen een jaar praktische resultaten geboekt, met meer dan 80 deelnemende partijen: lokale voedselinitiatieven, boeren, restauratiegroepen, bedrijven en sociale ondernemingen en de Universiteit Utrecht, die werkten aan 5 SFSC- en regeneratieprojecten, financieringstrajecten voor schaalvergroting, programma's voor jonge ondernemers en onderzoeksprojecten.